

Embracing urban livestock keeping in Tanzania: Exploring the institutional framework

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Abstract

While urban livestock keeping has persistently existed as an important livelihood strategy, there have been limited efforts to actively support its development. There are few and inefficient institutions which are involved in addressing the concerns associated with urban livestock keeping. Despite livestock keeping in urban areas being associated with poor solid waste disposal, poor sanitation practices, water contamination, odor and spread of diseases which often cause conflict with urban authorities, the policies, laws, by-laws, and regulations that guide livestock keeping seem to be unknown, weak, inadequate, or even not enforced. The frequent occurrence of environmental pollution with consequent conflicts calls for government and other stakeholders to take active measures geared towards making urban livestock keeping sustainable. There is also an urgent need to assess the adequacy of the current institutions in managing urban livestock keeping and come up with concrete measures for developing an institutional framework for sustainable urban livestock keeping in Tanzania.

Keywords: urban livestock keeping, institutional framework

1.0 Introductory background

1.1 urban livestock keeping: global phenomenon

It is believed that urban livestock keeping is one of the oldest and worldwide phenomena and that it is almost impossible to imagine development in cities without livestock (Thys et al, 2006). Throughout history, livestock has played a varied and dynamic role in rural and urban societies: food, employment, incomes, security, fuel, transport, and produce value-added goods which can have multiplier effects and create a need for services. Furthermore, livestock form a major capital reserve of farming households, diversify production, enhance crop production and spread risk (Seré and Steinfeld, 1996). Consequently, the importance of urban livestock is currently becoming increasingly recognized, particularly in developing countries where the majority of urban dwellers are poor (Scierre and Hoek, 2001). Urban livestock keeping is well suited to the Global Sustainable Development Goals 1, 2, 3, 12 and 13 of ending poverty in all its forms everywhere; ending hunger, achieving food security and improved nutrition, promoting sustainable agriculture; ensuring healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages; ensuring sustainable consumption and production patterns and, taking urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts.

Under the contemporary development challenges, the motive behind urban livestock keeping is varied from one class of people to the other. While the poor engage in livestock keeping as a response to limited alternative livelihood options and food insecurity, the middle-income families who normally have access to basic inputs such as land, labour and capital, on the other hand, engage in livestock keeping as a commercial activity to supplement household income in response to a growing urban demand and markets (Fuller, 2003; DFID, 2002).

It is estimated that 800 million urban residents worldwide are dealing with urban agriculture (FAO, 1999). In the light of this substantial number of people dealing with urban agriculture, it has now been recognized as a new development strategy, and thus attracting attention from donors, researchers and development organizations. (Ayaga et al, 2005; FAO, 2007). In African countries, 40% of urban dwellers are said to be engaged in some sort of agricultural activities and this percentage rises to 50% in Latin American countries. In Sub-

Saharan Africa, about 35% of urban dwellers are involved in urban agriculture (Prain, G. and Lee-Smith D. 2010; Beall and Fox, 2007). It is estimated that 23% of the total urban households in Tanzania engage in livestock keeping which contributes 14% of their income (URT, 2016; Covarrubias et al, 2012).

1.2 Urban livestock farming: a wanted business

Urban livestock keeping is beneficial. In Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, regardless of the unwanted consequences of livestock keeping due to insufficiently developed urban infrastructure along with the vast horizontal expansion of the city coupled with population growth rate of well over 5%, there is still big increasing demand for animal products. Women are found to be actively involved in urban livestock keeping as they own about 43% of dairy cattle, 81% of chickens, 47% of sheep and 33% of goats. In another study by Guendel (2002) in East Africa (Dar es Salaam, Kampala, Kisumu, Nairobi, and Addis Ababa), it was found out that urban livestock keeping benefits the poor, provides a way of diversifying livelihood activities that are accessible to vulnerable groups, and provides a source of locally produced food products for people living in the vicinity of the livestock keepers, is multi-purpose activity, has higher return per unit of land compared to crops, is flexible in terms of land use, it uses waste resources, and it provides a social safety net for the poor. This implies that urban livestock keeping forms an important livelihood base for urban dwellers as it contributes to household food security.

1.3 Urban livestock keeping: environmental pollution agent

Nonetheless, urban livestock keeping is associated with environmental pollution, the spread of diseases, invasion and damage of gardens, fences, lawns and ornamental plants causing formidable resistance from other non-livestock keepers (Mlozi et al., 2012; Mvena, Gaynor, 2007; Fuller, 2003; Smit et al, 2001).

1.4 Urban livestock keeping: poor in institutions

Regardless of the benefits of urban livestock keeping and the associated problems it causes, this seems to be an area whose institutional environment has not very well been developed. Some urban authorities prohibit certain animal types that are considered to

pose a nuisance and significant risk to health (Butler, 2012). It has been observed that sustainable urban livestock keeping in developing countries is largely ignored by policy-makers and constrained by the inadequate institutional framework for the control of development and management of institutions of urban livestock keeping (FAO, 2008; Wapwera, et al., 2015; Mwalukasa, 1999).

A Bureau for Animal Resources of the African Union (AU) organized a regional overview of a preliminary consultation in the Greater Horn of Africa to assess the institutional and policy support to the livestock sub-sector in Africa. The workshop members observed that although the constraints related to production, marketing, service provision, research, and technology transfer were well-known, the policy and institutional considerations underlying these constraints were either not recognized, targeted or addressed altogether (AU, 2004).

In a study by Ishagi et al., (2003), it is pointed out that livestock production among the urban and peri-urban poor is a sector that has not received the due attention it deserves. It is clear that Kampala City Council has officially recognized the importance of urban and peri-urban livestock keeping to the livelihood of its residents, but there is evidently a legislative gap. In another study in Kenya by Ayaga et al., (2004), it is pointed out clearly that although urban livestock keeping alleviates hunger and poverty for those who lack wage-employment, it also carries health risks in built-up areas. The study points out to the fact that although the Government of Kenya provides limited extension services to urban farmers, there is no coherent legal and policy framework governing urban agriculture and it, therefore, calls for coherent policy formulation and the follow-up on the policies that regulate urban livestock keeping. This observation is supported by Richards and Godfrey (2003) who carried out their study in Dar es Salaam, Kampala, Kisumu, and Nairobi and found that while the urban livestock keeping is on the increase, particularly among the poorest section of society, there were few, if any, institutions representing the needs of resource-poor urban livestock keepers. It also found out that urban livestock keeping was perceived to be illegal and a public health threat by most city authorities, often accompanied by harassment.

According to Fuller (2003), among the limitations confronting urban livestock keepers, institutional constraints is one of them. Others are socio-cultural biases; access to inputs, resources, and services; constraints post-production, especially marketing and processing; organizational constraints, and; risks related to farming in the city.

These deserve proper attention by policymakers to make urban livestock keeping productive and sustainable.

According to Cann et al., (2011), the total ban of livestock keeping (due to the problematic situations) has practically been impossible even in developed countries where there are well established municipal ordinances because livestock keepers have strong, organized resistances. Yet, formalization of urban agriculture and particularly livestock keeping, in terms of institutional and policy recognition has generally continued to be difficult, except in few cities such as Kampala and Nakuru, where ordinances governing urban agriculture have recently been put in place (Sabiiti et al, 2014). There is now an international agreement that prohibits the banning of urban livestock husbandry since it is neither socially nor politically acceptable. Instead, it is being recommended to create more suitable framework conditions and support of solution strategies (Morstein, 2017). Consequently, many development practitioners in Africa have come to the consensus that the most appropriate way to support the increasing population and urbanization is to develop a livestock policy that focuses on poverty alleviation among the increasing population.

2.0 Issue: Urban livestock keeping institutional framework

This global phenomenon of urban livestock keeping has got benefits and problems, as it has been seen. What is clear, though, is that much as this is supposed to be an area of great concern to policy-makers, there is little attention as the institutional framework to guide urban livelihood keeping is not well developed. What is the situation in Tanzania and what could be suggested in view of the established situation?

3.0 Methods and materials

This study is desk-based. A number of documents have been reviewed, together with the literature on urban livestock keeping in Tanzania. Among the reviewed documents are: National Livestock Policy (URT, 2006), Town and Country Planning Ordinance (CAP 378), (Urban farming) Regulations 1992, *Siasa ni Kilimo* of 1972, *Kilimo cha Umwagiliaji* of 1974, *Kilimo cha Kufa na Kupona, Mvua za Kwanza ni za Kupandia* of 1974/75, the National Economic Survival Programme (NESP) of 1981/82, the National Food Strategy of 1982, Tanzania National Livestock Policy (URT, 2006), the National Agricultural Policy (NAP) of 1983, and National Economic Recovery Programme (ERP) of

1986-1990, Human settlement Policy (URT 2000), Livestock Sector Development Strategy (URT, 2010), Livestock Sector Development Programme (URT, 2011), and the Tanzania Livestock Modernization Initiative (URT 2015).

After reviewing all these documents, plus some critical literature regarding urban animal keeping in Tanzania, a thematic analysis was deployed rotating around the following key themes: institutional environment, urban livestock keeping practices, and institutional limitations. These are the areas in which the findings are based.

3.0 Findings

3.1 Institutional environment

Foeken (2005) observes that urban agriculture in Tanzania is practiced in a generally favorable political and legal context and has been a recognized activity since the beginning of the 1970s. He accounts for the basis of this recognition as emanating from poor economic performance in the 1970s and 1980s, which forced the government to formulate policies which, among other things, encouraged urban dwellers to undertake urban agriculture to attain food self-sufficiency. Among the Government policies used by political leaders to encourage urban dwellers raise livestock and grow food crops in their backyards and on other open spaces include *Siasa ni Kilimo* ("Politics is agriculture") of 1972, *Kilimo cha Umwagiliaji* (Irrigated agriculture") in 1974, *Kilimo cha Kufa na Kupona* ("Agriculture for life and death"), *Mvua za Kwanza ni za Kupandia* ("First rains are for planting") in 1974/75, the National Economic Survival Programme (NESP) of 1981/82, the National Food Strategy of 1982, the National Livestock Policy (NLP) and the National Agricultural Policy (NAP) of 1983, and the National Economic Recovery Programme (ERP) of 1986-1990.

The National Livestock Policy (URT, 2006) acknowledges the existence of urban and peri-urban livestock farming that is practiced in all towns and cities in Tanzania and that dairy and beef cattle, poultry, pigs, and pets are some of the animals kept. It also calls for the promotion of this type of production system because of its potential to provide employment, income and supplementary source of livestock products to town dwellers for food security by strengthening technical support services and encouraging livestock farming that is environmentally friendly. This policy also recognizes the fact that

urban livestock keeping is constrained by diseases, poor quality feeds, inadequate technical support services, low genetic potential of the local breed, weak farmer organizations, inadequate regulatory framework, inadequate land, insufficient supply of quality stocks and inputs, conflicts among communities, inadequate expertise, pollution and unorganized markets.

Analyzing the statutory basis of urban farming in general, and urban livestock keeping in particular based on the current Town and Country Planning Ordinance (CAP 378), (Urban farming) Regulations 1992, "urban farming" is defined as carrying out of plant and animal husbandry activities within statutory township boundaries. Two regulations in the Ordinance state that: (i) no person shall occupy or use more than three acres of land for urban farming; and (ii) no person shall, except where that person practices zero-grazing, graze his animal in an urban area" (Government Notice No. 10, of 5/2/93, p.10). This implies that an open urban livestock keeping is essentially unwelcomed, but where it is practiced under strict adherence to the regulations, the number of animals that can be reared is restricted for reasons of hygiene, environmental hazards, social nuisance, and accidents. The two examples taken from these regulations are the basis upon which most urban authorities in Tanzania prohibit urban farming in general and livestock keeping in particular.

Although all urban local government authorities have Livestock and Fisheries Development whose activities focused on the provision of extension services to small farmers on animal health care, products' processing, and marketing, enforcement of relevant by-laws particularly on zero-grazing has generally not been successful. Foeken (2005) underscores the fact that the by-laws frequently used the date from colonial times and they forbid all agricultural activity within the boundaries of urban centers. He asserts that this is typically the western perception of what constitutes 'urban' where urban livestock keeping is supposed to cause all kinds of environmental hazards, and therefore, unwanted.

Despite the importance of urban agriculture in sustainable development, if not properly practiced it conflicts with other urban land uses and leads to land degradation, water pollution, and is a threat to health and safety. Consequently, the Human Settlement Policy (URT 2000), sets the following policy goals:

1. To designate special areas within planning areas whereby people will be granted legal rights to engage in agricultural activities;

2. To continue to regulate and research the conduct of urban agriculture and to ensure that it does not disrupt planned urban development;
3. To review existing laws to facilitate planned urban agriculture; and
4. To facilitate the construction of appropriate infrastructure to prevent land degradation, water pollution, and health and safety hazards in areas where urban agriculture is permitted.

In essence, these by-laws point to the fact that urban agriculture is an illegal activity in most of the built-up areas of municipalities in Tanzania.

3.2 Urban Livestock keeping practices

Perhaps one of the reasons why the government is not taking serious steps to address the seemingly impending challenges confronting urban livestock keeping is that the activity is transient and will find its proper place in the periphery of the urban areas in the near future. As urban areas expand, agricultural land is lost to other uses (Mwalukasa, 1999). This position is supported by a study by Mlozi, et al., (2012), on the effects of climatic change due to keeping livestock in urban and peri-urban areas of Dar-es-salaam, who found that half of the respondents (54%) who kept livestock said that in the future they would zero-graze their cattle to cope with the scarcity of forage, slightly less than half (49%) said they would in the future reduce the number of dairy cattle by half, and third of the respondents (37%) said that in the future they would stop keeping dairy cattle and do businesses instead. This implies that urban livestock keeping is not considered as being permanent and viable activity by its key stakeholders to warrant regulative measures of permanency nature.

3.3 Urban livestock keeping institutional limitations

The Tanzania National Livestock Policy (URT, 2006) provides for clear roles and responsibilities of stakeholders including private and public sectors in addressing concerns on urban livestock keeping but falls short of an effective institutional framework and adequate capacity for effective implementation of the policy. Similarly, although the Livestock Sector Development Strategy (URT, 2010) admits that commercial poultry production is concentrated in urban and peri-urban areas, it ends presenting no specific strategy for improving

urban livestock keeping in Tanzania. There are no specific measures contained in this document that are exclusively meant to deal with the known problems confronting urban livestock keeping.

Another important initiative taken to deal with livestock sector was the Livestock Sector Development Programme (URT, 2011). The Programme was formulated with a view to transforming the livestock sector from its current status to a modern one with the potential for a progressive livestock sector which is economically, socially and environmentally sustainable. Although the programme was conceived as a useful instrument of poverty reduction in which service delivery needed to be strengthened in line with the National Livestock Policy after several decades of not receiving proper attention as required, there is no specific mention in the programme components and interventions of how it will address the concerns related to urban livestock keeping. This lack of special programme attention on urban livestock keeping presents a formidable obstacle to sustainable urban livestock keeping in the country.

In the Tanzania Livestock Modernization Initiative (TLMI), it is categorically stated that "the Government of Tanzania is committed to working closely with the private sector from within and outside the country in unleashing the immense potential for developing the livestock sector for the benefit of rural communities and to improve national health and nutritional standards " (URT, 2015). TLMI uses the 2012/13 National Panel Survey (NPS) livestock data as a basis for developing the goal, purpose, objectives, and strategies. There is an apparent oversight in the Initiative of taking urban livestock keeping on board. There is no any mention of the urban livestock keeping and therefore sidelines it in favor of rural areas.

Among the most recent initiatives to provide a comprehensive review of smallholder livestock sector in Tanzania is contained in the report which also uses the 2012/13 National Panel Survey (NPS) livestock data. Again, this report concentrates its review on livestock keeping in rural areas, with a very limited mention on urban livestock keeping. In this report, it is stated that 62% of rural households depend on domesticated animals for their livelihoods with an average of 20 animals per household (URT, 2016). Compared with the 23% of urban households involved in livestock keeping for only 14% of their income, there is an obvious temptation of not taking urban livestock keeping seriously!

4.0 Conclusion and recommendation

The circumstance in which urban livestock keeping is practiced is, however, not straightforward: policies, the statutory base, and by-laws are either not clearly known, inadequate, or not fully enforced. Actions taken by urban authorities against those who breach the regulations have been sporadic, ad hoc, and unsustainable, thus calling for a more systematic approach to urban livestock management (Angello et al., 2016).

There is clearly a need for an Institutional framework for sustainable urban livestock keeping in Tanzania. In view of the current patchy, sporadic and localized institutions of urban livestock keeping, it is difficult to achieve sustainable livelihoods based on urban livestock keeping. Many studies (Angello, et al., 2016, Burke, et al., 2012, and Sikika, 2010) have identified the shortage of required staff as one of the major constraints of institutional effectiveness, of which Sikika refers to "a crisis in human resources". So, there is a shortage of Livestock Officers, Public Health Officers and Environmental Management Officers who are the main source of information on livestock husbandry practices. Angello, et al, (2016) attempted to assess the general awareness of the institutions for urban livestock keepers. They found that very few respondents mentioned by-laws, and it was not clear as to whether this was due to livestock keepers' ignorance on their existence, or they didn't consider them important since they were part and parcel of urban livestock keeping.

There is a need, therefore, to understand how to establish an effective institutional framework for addressing problems of environmental pollution and conflicts caused by urban livestock keeping in Tanzania (AU, 2004; URT, 2011). An inquiry on the potency of the current institutional arrangements for urban livestock keeping is needed. We propose a study to assess the potency of current institutions (policies, regulations, and by-laws) in addressing the challenges of urban livestock keeping with a view to proposing measures for improving the institutional framework for sustainable urban livestock keeping in Tanzania.

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